

Supplementary material to :

Note on the problem of considering the presence of wall in the modeling of chromatographic columns

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The column model

A chromatographic column can be approximated by a cylindrical tube filled with adsorbent as shown in Fig. 1. The heat balance model incorporates heat transfer within the cylindrical tube and porous column packing immersed in mobile phase, whereas mass and momentum balance models refer to space occupied by column packing.

Heat balances for:

- porous packing

$$\begin{aligned} & (\varepsilon_t C_{P,m} + (1 - \varepsilon_t) C_{P,s}) \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - \varepsilon_t T \alpha \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + C_{P,m} u_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + C_{P,m} u_r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \\ & = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \lambda_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\lambda_{eff} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) - (1 - \varepsilon_t) \sum_{i=1}^{NC} (\Delta H_i) \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} - u_x (1 - \alpha T) \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} - u_r (1 - \alpha T) \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} \end{aligned}$$

- column walls

$$C_{P,w} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\lambda_w}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \lambda_w \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2}$$

Momentum balance:

$$\varepsilon_t \left(\frac{\partial q}{\partial P} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q}{\partial T} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \right) - \text{div} \left(\rho \cdot \frac{\kappa}{\eta} \text{grad}(P) \right) = 0$$

Mass balance for:

- porous packing

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + \frac{(1 - \varepsilon_t) \partial q}{\varepsilon_t \partial t} + \frac{1}{\varepsilon_t} \text{div}(c \cdot \mathbf{u}) = \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \left(D_{a,x} \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \left(r D_{a,r} \frac{\partial c}{\partial r} \right)$$

Figure S1. Chromatographic column model

The heat balance

The heat balance model involves separate equations for column packing bed consisting of stationary phase and interstitial liquid, Eq. (1), and for column wall, Eq. (2). The chromatographic column is described by its basic geometry: internal radius R_{in} [m], external radius R_{out} [m], and length L [m]. Due to column symmetry the equations are expressed as follows using cylindrical coordinates.

The total bed porosity ε_t in the heat balance equation (Eq. (1)) is calculated from Eq. (S1):

$$\varepsilon_t = \varepsilon_e + \varepsilon_p(1 - \varepsilon_e) \quad (S1)$$

where ε_e is the external porosity of the bed, ε_p is the particle shell porosity.

The mobile phase thermal expansion coefficient α in Eq. (1) is calculated from Eq. (S2):

$$\alpha = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{d\rho}{dT} \quad (S2)$$

where ρ is the local density of the mobile phase.

The effective thermal conductivity (λ_{eff}) of the solid porous bed immersed in the eluent was in our studies calculated according to Zarichnyak [1] with the following equation:

$$\lambda_{eff} = \varepsilon_t^2 \lambda_{el} + (1 - \varepsilon_t)^2 \lambda_s + 4\varepsilon_t(1 - \varepsilon_t) \frac{\lambda_{el}\lambda_s}{\lambda_{el} + \lambda_s} \quad (S3)$$

where λ_{el} [$W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$] and λ_s [$W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$] are eluent and silica particles thermal conductivities, respectively.

The momentum balance

The momentum balance model Eq. (S6) can be created by combination of the continuity equation (Eq.(S4)):

$$\varepsilon_t \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + div(\rho \cdot \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (S4)$$

with Darcy's law (Eq.(S5)):

$$\mathbf{u} = -\frac{\kappa}{\eta} grad(P) \quad (S5)$$

giving the following equation:

$$\varepsilon_t \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} - div\left(\rho \cdot \frac{\kappa}{\eta} grad(P)\right) = 0 \quad (S6)$$

Since the local fluid density ρ is changing with time but also with local temperature and local pressure one can apply the following chain rule:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial P} \frac{\partial P}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (S7)$$

Subsequently, Eq. (S6) can be rewritten in the form shown as Eq. 12.

The bed permeability coefficient κ in the above equations can be calculated as proposed by Bird et al. [2]. for given packing particle diameter d_p and bed external porosity ε_e :

$$\kappa = \frac{d_p^2 \varepsilon_e^3}{150(1-\varepsilon_e)^2} \quad (S8)$$

The mass balance

A mathematical model that allows describing the chromatography process for one component with required accuracy is the equilibrium-dispersive model (ED) that assumes the solute concentrations in the mobile and stationary phases to be in local equilibrium and accounts for the finite mass transfer between the phases through the apparent axial and radial dispersion coefficients. The two-dimensional ED model in cylindrical coordinates is expressed by Eq. (22)

It should be noticed that due to the fact that surface concentration q in Eq. (22) depends both on temperature T and concentration c , the time derivative of surface concentration can be approximated by formula based on the chain rule:

$$\frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial c_i} \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial T} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (S9)$$

The apparent axial dispersion coefficient $D_{ai,x}$ in the ED model (Eq. (22)) can be calculated from the following equation [3–5]:

$$D_{ai,x} = \frac{D_L \varepsilon_e}{\varepsilon_t} + \left(\frac{k_{zi}}{1+k_{zi}} \right)^2 \frac{u_x^2 d_p}{6 \varepsilon_t \varepsilon_e F_e} \left(\frac{\tau d_p}{10 \varepsilon_e D_{mi}} + \frac{1}{k_{ext}} \right) \quad (S10)$$

where D_L is the local dispersion coefficient [$\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$], D_{mi} is the molecular diffusion coefficient [$\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] of i -th solute, k_{ext} is the external mass transfer coefficient [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$], F_e is the phase ratio (Eq.(S11)):

$$F_e = \frac{1-\varepsilon_t}{\varepsilon_t} \quad (S11)$$

τ is the tortuosity coefficient [-] (Eq. (12)) [6]:

$$\tau = \varepsilon_p + 1.5(1 - \varepsilon_p) \quad (S12)$$

and k_{zi} is i -th solute zone retention factor [-] (Eq. (13)):

$$k_{zi} = \frac{1-\varepsilon_e}{\varepsilon_e} \left(\varepsilon_t + (1 - \varepsilon_t) \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial c_i} \right) \quad (S13)$$

The radial dispersion coefficient, $D_{ai,r}$, can be calculated based on the equation derived by Knox et al. [7]:

$$D_{ai,r} = \frac{0.03d_p u_x}{\varepsilon_t} + 0.7D_{mi} \quad (S14)$$

Different correlations describing the local dispersion coefficient, D_L are available in literature, i.e. by Gunn [8], by Wen and Fan [9], or by Chung and Wen [10]. In this paper the Chung and Wen approach was applied since it was proven to be the most accurate in our previous works [11,12]. According to the Chung and Wen model the local dispersion coefficient, D_L , can be calculated from the equation:

$$\frac{\varepsilon_e D_L}{u_x L} = \frac{\varepsilon_e d_p}{L} \frac{1}{0.2 + 0.011 Re^{0.48}} \quad (S15)$$

The molecular diffusion coefficient of i -th solute, D_{mi} , can be estimated using the Wilke–Chang equation [13]:

$$D_{mi} = 7.4 \cdot 10^{-12} \frac{(\phi M)^{0.5} T}{\eta V_i^{0.6}} \quad (S16)$$

where V_i is the molar volume of i -th solute at normal boiling point [$\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$], M is the molar mass of a solvent [$\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$] and ϕ is the association coefficient [-].

The external mass transfer coefficient k_{ext} , can be derived from the Wilson–Geankoplis correlation [14]:

$$Sh = \frac{1.09}{\varepsilon_e} Re^{0.33} Sc^{0.33} \quad (S17)$$

where Sh , Re , and Sc are the Sherwood, Reynolds, and Schmidt criterial numbers, respectively:

$$Sh = \frac{k_{ext} d_p}{D_m}, Re = \frac{u_x \rho d_p}{\eta}, Sc = \frac{\eta}{\rho D_m} \quad (S18)$$

Numerical methods and calculation details

The orthogonal collocation on finite elements (OCFE) algorithm was applied for approximation of the spatial derivatives in the ODE. Following this algorithm, the column model domain was divided into subdomains (referred to as finite elements) along and across the column axis. In each subdomain, number of internal collocation points

(NICP) are selected as the roots of the NICP-th order Legendre polynomial. The details of the applied spatial discretization are given in Table S1.

Table S1. Spatial discretization applied in the solution

Number of subdomains in x direction	50
Number of collocation points in each subdomain in x direction	3
Number of subdomains in r direction	2
Number of collocation points in each subdomain in r direction within the column packing region	7
Number of collocation points in each subdomain in r direction within the column wall region	3

The parameters' values used for simulations are presented in Table S2.

Table S2. Values of parameters applied in calculations

Parameter	Symbol [unit]	Value
Column length	L [mm]	100
Column inner radius	R_{in} [mm]	1.05, 2.3, 5
Column outer radius	R_{out} [mm]	3.2, 4, 6.35
Particle size	d_p [μm]	5
Total porosity	ε_t [-]	0.642
External porosity	ε_e [-]	0.379
Particle porosity	ε_p [-]	0.429
Thermal conductivity coefficient of packing (silica)	λ_s [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]	0.978
Thermal conductivity coefficient of stainless steel wall	λ_{ws} [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]	16
Thermal conductivity coefficient of PEEK wall	λ_{wp} [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]	0.25
External heat transfer coefficient	h_{ext} [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$]	0.001, 10, 1000
Inlet and initial temperature	T_{in} [K]	323

External temperature	T_{ext} [K]	323
Fluid superficial velocity at the column inlet	u_{x0} [$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$]	0.001
Adsorption enthalpy	ΔH [$\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$]	0, -10, -20, -40, -60
Isotherm parameter	q_0 [$\text{m}^3\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$]	2
Isotherm parameter	K_0 [$\text{m}^3\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$]	0.001
Universal gas constant	R [$\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]	8.314
Inlet solute concentration	c_0 [$\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$]	0.01, 0.1, 1
Solute injection time	t_{inj} [s]	30
Solute molar volume	V [$\text{cm}^3\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$]	89.0
Solvent association coefficient (for water)	ϕ [-]	2.26

Analytical stainless steel and PEEK columns in preparative conditions

The model solution results for 2.1 mm diameter columns were obtained under preparative conditions, i.e. with the inlet concentration of the solute increased 10 times ($c_0 = 0.1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, cases S21-C100 and P21-C100 in Fig. S2) and 100 times ($c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, case S21-C1000 in Fig. 4 and case P21-C1000 in Fig. S3).

Figure S2. Simulation results obtained for chromatographic columns operated under analytical conditions with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 0.1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profile in 2.1 mm stainless steel column, b) outlet temperature profile in 2.1 mm stainless steel column, c) concentration profile in 2.1 mm PEEK column, d) outlet temperature profile in 2.1 mm PEEK column

Figure S3. Simulation results obtained for chromatographic columns operated under analytical conditions with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profile in 2.1 mm PEEK column, b) outlet temperature profile in 2.1 mm PEEK column

Preparative column in preparative condition

The next step in the simulations was to investigate the effect of the presence of column walls in models of chromatographic columns with much larger cross-sections comparing to typical analytical columns, loaded with the highest considered inlet concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ of a solute. Columns of dimensions

4.6 mm (ID) x 8 mm (OD) x 100 mm (length) and 10.0 (ID) x 12.7 mm (OD) x 100 mm (length) were examined (cases S46-C1000, S100-1000, P46-C1000, P100-C1000).

Figure S4. Simulation results obtained for chromatographic column operated under preparative conditions with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profile in 4.6 mm PEEK column, b) outlet temperature profile in 4.6 mm PEEK column

Figure S5. Simulation results obtained for chromatographic column operated under preparative conditions with inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profile in 10 mm PEEK column, b) outlet temperature profile in 10 mm PEEK column

Effects of adsorption enthalpy on preparative column performance

The effects of adsorption heat was studied by performing calculations for different values of adsorption enthalpy values, i.e. $\Delta H = 0, -10, -20, -40$ and $-60 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, and as well as for different column thermal conditions. The arbitrary choice was a steel column with dimensions of 4.6 mm (ID) x 8 mm (OD) x 10 mm (L), into which the solute was injected at concentration of $1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. The remaining column and process parameters were assumed in accordance with Table 2.

Figure S6. Simulation results obtained for 4.6 mm chromatographic column and inlet solute concentration $c_0 = 1 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) concentration profiles for $h_{ext} = 0.001 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$, b) outlet temperature profile for $h_{ext} = 0.001 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$, c) concentration profiles for $h_{ext} = 10 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$, d) outlet temperature profile for $h_{ext} = 10 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$

Wall effects in a two-component chromatographic system

The presence of column wall in a chromatographic column model was also tested in a two-component system. The mathematical model describing such a case requires the introduction of another mass transport equation for the second component, as well as the definition of the equation parameters and the details of adsorption equilibrium in a two-component system. The case of a 4.6 mm (ID) \times 8 mm (OD) \times 100 mm (L) stainless steel column operating under near perfect insulation conditions ($h_{ext} = 0.001 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$) was selected for comparison with an analogous instance operated under adiabatic conditions (without column walls). The calculations assumed two solutes with a significant adsorption enthalpy value of $\Delta H = -60 \text{ kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, and in order to make the heat release analogous to the previously discussed cases, the inlet concentrations c_{0i} of both solutes were reduced to $0.5 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$. The remaining parameters of the calculations are given in Tables S2 and S3.

Table 4. Values of parameters applied in calculations for two-component system

Parameter	Symbol [unit]	Value
Adsorption enthalpy for solute 1	ΔH_1 [kJ·mol ⁻¹]	-60
Adsorption enthalpy for solute 2	ΔH_2 [kJ·mol ⁻¹]	-60
Isotherm parameter for solutes 1 and 2	q_0 [m ³ ·mol ⁻¹]	2
Isotherm parameter for solute 1	K_{01} [m ³ ·mol ⁻¹]	0.001
Isotherm parameter for solute 2	K_{02} [m ³ ·mol ⁻¹]	0.0007
Inlet concentration of both solutes	c_{0i} [mol·m ⁻³]	0.5
Mixture injection time	t_{inj} [s]	30
Molar volume of solute 1	V_1 [cm ³ ·mol ⁻¹]	89.0
Molar volume of solute 2	V_2 [cm ³ ·mol ⁻¹]	89.0

Figure S7. Simulation results obtained for 4.6 mm chromatographic column injected with a mixture of two solutes of identical inlet concentration $c_0 = 0.5 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$: a) outlet temperature profile under adiabatic conditions, b) outlet temperature profile for $h_{ext} = 0.001 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$

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